

Recommended citation: Gauk, M., & Eberhardt, J. (2021). Fraud Detection Using Watermarks in Examination Answers. In Heiß, H.-U., Järvinen, H.-M., Mayer, A., & Schulz, A. (Eds.), *Blended Learning in Engineering Education: challengingm enlightening and lasting? SEFI 49th Annual Conference* (pp. 855-862). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Berlin, Germany. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14650294.

FRAUD DETECTION USING WATERMARKS IN EXAMINATION ANSWERS

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Conference Key Areas: Online assessments

Keywords: remote examination, watermarking, fraud detection

ABSTRACT

Most examinations at TU Berlin had to be conducted online due to the COVID-19 outbreak and lockdowns during the winter term 2020/21. Although most exams were designed to be open-book or non-collaborative take-home exams, it enabled students to commit fraud by collaborating. Therefore, we implemented a method in the Moodle LMS to detect copied answers by adding individual watermarks while the students type their answers. If a student were to copy their answer out of the textbox and share it with their classmates (e.g. via an instant messaging service) who then paste the answer into their own textboxes, the system would be able to recognize the watermarks and who copied from whom. The text watermarks are invisible (by using non-printing Unicode characters) and will not get lost while copying. The system is able to reliably detect fraud if students use the described approach. Even though the students were made aware of a fraud detection system, a very small percentage of cheaters were still able to be exposed by it. There is a possibility that many others cheated through other means (e.g. by sharing screenshots) that are hard or impossible to be detected. The collaborations that were detected took place only in exams that consisted of no or a very small number of random questions. Accordingly, building a large question bank is one of the most effective ways to stop students from easily collaborating during an exam.

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1 INTRODUCTION

All students should take an examination under the same conditions that allow their results to be comparable. Usually, the teaching staff ensures that by supervising the students and checking whether they collaborate or use forbidden reference materials. As a consequence of the COVID-19 outbreak and lockdowns, most examinations at Technische Universität Berlin had to be conducted online from remote during the winter term 2020/2021. The assumption is that more students than before now try to cheat as they feel confident enough that their attempted fraud cannot be detected. Since there are numerous ways to cheat and to access disallowed resources, one important measure was to design the exams to be open-book or take-home exams and allowing the students to use all resources that are not communication tools. Before they can start their exam attempt, our students had to log in to our Moodle learning management system (LMS) with a two-factor authentication method and they had to make an affidavit to work on their exam autonomously, that they do not receive help from any third party and that they do not provide any help to others. We were not allowed to use proctoring solutions because of privacy and missing legislative basis. We also did not force use of the Safe Exam Browser (SEB) as this software is not available for Linux and the security means are bypassed easily (e.g. students can use a second device).

We assumed that the students who collaborate share their answers via instant messaging services. Hence, we concentrated on trying to unveil some of these collaborations and implemented a method in Moodle quizzes that inserts invisible individual watermarks into the questions and student's answers using text and image watermarking, allowing to detect copied answers and to identify who shared their answers. These watermarks are preserved even when an answer is copied and pasted multiple times through messengers. Since we made the students aware of a fraud detection system, we hoped to prevent fraud on a psychological level.

2 BACKGROUND

2.1 Digital Watermarking

Watermarks are classified as visible and invisible. Visible watermarks usually consist of a noticeable text or a logo and invisible watermarks are not or hardly perceptible to the human eye. Digital watermarking may be used for ownership assertion, fingerprints, copy control, or fraud detection by embedding information somewhere in a way that it can later be extracted or detected [1]. There are multiple possible ways to embed watermarks in videos, images, audio files, and documents like PDF files, but they can also be put in plain texts. Traditional approaches display the text as an image and include the watermark in that image, or they modify sentences while keeping their meaning (e.g. by passivating clauses or substituting words with synonyms) [2]. Watermarks can be embedded in images by slightly modifying the luminance of some pixels in a way that it is detectable by machines but hardly perceptible to a human [3].

2.2 Unicode

Unicode is a standard that describes the digital encoding and representation of letters and other characters. Each character is assigned a *code point* (a numerical value) and Unicode may define up to 1,114,112 *code points* (in the hexadecimal range of U+0 to U+10FFFF) with the aim to represent the characters of most of the world's languages. The most important Unicode encoding formats are *UTF-8* and *UTF-16*. The code points are encoded as up to four *code units* each consisting of a bit sequence of 8 bits (*UTF-8*) or up to two *code units* each consisting of 16 bits (*UTF-16*). [4]

2.3 Digital Text Watermarking

The Unicode standard does not intentionally provide a possibility to hide arbitrary data in a plain text. However, the various features and the large amount of 143,589 characters that are currently defined in Unicode allow to implement a digital watermarking for plain texts.

Homoglyphs are one option to be used as watermarks. These are characters or glyphs that appear very similar or identical, e.g. Latin letter 'j' (Unicode code point U+006a) and Cyrillic letter 'j' (U+0458) are visually identical in many fonts. The Unicode standard publishes a list of these visually confusable Characters. Homoglyphs can be used to encode the bit sequence of watermarking data. Whenever a confusable letter is found in a text, it represents one part of the bit sequence (by leaving the original symbol or replacing it with a homoglyph) [5]. Usually, this method is only able to encode one bit per symbol since there are not so many confusable characters. Accordingly, the text must have a specific minimum length that there is a chance to embed the whole watermark data.

Unicode also defines several space characters of different widths (from hair space to quad space), which allows embedding more than just one bit of the watermark bits per space. A drawback is that the different space widths might catch the reader's eye and thus be too distracting in plain texts [6].

There are also special non-printing characters in Unicode, such as zero-width joiner, non-joiner [7] and tag characters. They provide a way to hide the watermark data in a text, and they allow embedding two or more bits per code point. Additionally, the non-printing characters can be put together to form the whole watermark. They also can be repeated throughout the text as often as needed. Hence, the watermark could also be embedded in very short texts. However, this method may heavily increase the text size (in bytes), while homoglyph approaches might not or only slightly influence the text size.

The Unicode tag characters (U+E0000 to U+E007F) are used to insert information separate from the ordinary text. They are utilized in *emoji flag sequences* as a modifier to display national flags. Initially, these code points were supposed to provide a language tagging feature for texts, which has been deprecated since.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

When watermarks should be embedded in examination questions and answers, the main issues are:

- *Capacity*: How much information/data (in bits) can be inserted in an answer? Exam answers might be very short (only one digit/character).
- *Transparency*: How do you embed the information in a way that it is hardly perceptible to the human eye and cannot be noticed when writing, copying, and editing the exam answer? First of all, the watermarking must not disturb or distract the students during writing their own answers.
- *Reliability*: How can you reliably determine that someone copied/pasted an answer and from whom? How do you prevent false accusation when someone maliciously or accidentally modifies the watermark?
- *Robustness*: The watermarks should not get lost when an answer is copied and pasted multiple times and when they are shared via instant messaging services or collaboration tools.

We wanted to implement two completely different approaches of watermarking an examination: (1) Text watermarking using non-printing Unicode characters and (2) watermarking the exam's

website background.

We assumed that the students who collaborate during the remote exam primarily stay in touch with their classmates (during the COVID-19 outbreak and lockdowns) via instant messaging services or via real-time collaboration tools like Google Docs. They might copy their answers out of their textboxes or they might take screenshots and share that. The purpose of the watermarking is to identify both the person who shared their answers and the person who copied/pasted the answer. However, watermarking the website background only helps in the rare case when someone posts the screenshots on a public website or publicly available chat rooms.

The watermarking is implemented as a Moodle plugin and core modifications¹. When a student starts a new quiz (exam) attempt, a 64 bit random unsigned integer will be generated, which serves as a unique identifier of the student and the quiz attempt. We agreed with our data protection officers to delete these identifiers 30 days after the exam took place. Since we only consider the watermarks within one exam, even a much smaller integer could prove to be sufficient (our largest exam has about 1,300 participants). However, we wanted to reduce the risk of false accusation in case someone accidentally modifies their watermark and that watermark now matches someone else's identifier by a coincidence. This is why we chose that the watermark has to consist of at least 32 bit of this identifier.

When the student views an exam page, the watermark is embedded on the client side using JavaScript. When a teacher views an exam attempt, the student's watermark will not be embedded to avoid that the teacher accidentally distributes the identifiers. In fact, our teachers cannot access tables or reports with the students' watermarks.

The watermarking functionality has to be enabled by a teacher in the Moodle quiz settings. Just before starting an examination attempt, the students are made aware of this fraud detection system ("The exam is protected by security measures, which reveals your identity if you share answers or screenshots!").

3.1 Text Watermarking

We explored the different approaches of digital text watermarking regarding the main issues and implementation effort. The homoglyphs and whitespace approach is unsuitable for examinations because they offer too few data capacity and they are not applicable to short exam answers like numerical answers.

The Unicode tag characters were promising because contemporary Windows, Linux and Android systems do not display these characters at all, and the range U+E000 to U+E007F would allow placing seven bits of the watermark data within one character. However, we identified that iOS 14.4 displays most of these characters as a question mark and only the range U+E0061 to U+E007A as a whitespace (all neighboring tag characters are displayed as one space as long as there is no other character in-between). The characters are invisible starting from Windows 7 (Windows XP displays them as empty boxes). The instant messengers WhatsApp, Discord and Matrix/Element as well as Google Docs preserve them. Telegram's desktop client removes the tag characters, while Telegram's Android and web client keeps them (at the time this report was made).

The four zero-width characters U+2060 to U+2063 (word joiner, function application, invisible times and invisible separator [4]) allow to embed two bits per characters. We also checked these characters under the mentioned operating systems and applications, and found that they preserve these characters and do not display them.

¹The source code is available under: https://github.com/innocampus/moodle-quizaccess_watermark

A double click also highlights the adjacent tag and zero-width characters. In Linux and Windows, we observed that Firefox highlights the characters before and after the word, while Chrome only highlights the code points that are after the word that a user has double clicked on.

We decided to make use of both the tag characters and zero-width characters in order to ensure that at least one of them are preserved when copying and sharing answers. Due to the limitations imposed by iOS, we only use the range U+E0061 to U+E0071, which allows us to embed four bits per character. We modified the exam web page's text input fields to insert the zero-width characters at the beginning of the text and before each space. The tag characters are inserted after each space and at the end of the text. The text is modified only when the student leaves a textbox and at the moment when they highlight something.

Whenever the watermark is embedded using tag characters, we insert 16 tag characters at the same time, which allows to embed the whole 64 bit identifier. This watermark consumes 64 bytes in UTF-8 since each of these code points needs four code units. We also insert 16 of the zero-width characters. Since they embed just two bits, we can only take the first 32 bits (beginning with the most significant bit) of the identifier. This consumes 48 bytes in UTF-8 because each of the code points takes three code units. In total, each space (one byte) now requires 112 bytes additionally, which greatly increases the memory consumption of the text input fields. We consider this being acceptable.

We do not put the watermark in the middle of a word, which would break all spellcheckers and distract the students. In addition, the tag characters are displayed as one space in iOS, which would be distracting too within a word. However, the gap between two words is still a little wider than normally in iOS. We observed that we can safely insert the watermarks into the input fields of Moodle's short answer, numerical, calculated, and cloze question types.

Despite the characters being invisible, the students may still notice them when they hit their arrow or backspace/delete keys. These keys skip or remove one character after another, but the user does not immediately see anything happening because there are so many of these invisible characters. It seems as the cursor cannot move forward and, obviously, this would be too confusing. Hence, we implemented a logic on the exam website that adjusts the cursor accordingly and makes it behaving as expected.

When a student submits their answers, we remove the watermarks (using regular expressions) on the server side as Moodle would evaluate the answers wrong. The raw answers (including the watermarks) are saved in a separate database table.

Finally, we implemented the watermark detection and reporting functionality. All foreign identifiers that are found in the answers, i.e., all identifiers that do not belong to the student, are reported and the system tries to find and name the answer's actual author. The system searches for the author only within the same exam.

3.2 Website Background Watermarking

We modified the exam's website background by inserting an SVG background image that appears identical to the usual background. The watermark is embedded by modifying the luminance of certain pixels at a fixed position and there are 64 pixels that encode the whole student's unique identifier. A modified (slightly brighter) pixel denotes bit 1 and an unmodified pixel bit 0 (Figure 1). We also insert one slightly darker pixel that indicates the beginning of the watermark. It is located left to the first pixel that refers to the identifier's most significant bit. The SVG image has a size of 90x90 pixels and it is repeated (horizontally and vertically) to cover the whole exam's questions and answers background area.

Figure 1: Stretched example of an SVG background tile with the embedded identifier *0x0123456789abcdef*. The left image consists of highlighted pixels for better visuals (blue=1, white=0, black=beginning).

Figure 2: Image watermarking with the embedded identifier *0x101217303637f3f0*, partially filled.

This image watermarking method is very simple, but it is sufficient in this case because we only want to deal with screenshots. Since screenshots are perfect copies usually, we do not have to consider printing errors, and therefore error correction algorithms are not necessary.

When we need to extract a watermark from a screenshot, we do that manually with the help of a graphics editor by filling the background with an inverse color (as seen in Figure 2) and identifying all pixels that differ. That way, we are able to determine the student's identifier and to look up this identifier in the database.

4 RESULTS

The watermarking feature was enabled in 58 exams, distributed nearly equally across all faculties. This number is much smaller than the actual number of examinations because we finished the Moodle plugin after our winter term's examination session already started and we advised teachers to enable the watermarking feature only in mock exams for the moment. After one week we were confident enough that this feature can be enabled safely in real exams too, but left the final decision up to each teacher. We only counted exams that consisted of questions with answer fields where it was possible to embed a watermark. 24 exams with 1945 participants were omitted because they only consisted of single/multiple choice, drag & drop or essay questions.

	No. of exams	No. of participants	Collaborations
All exams and mock exams	90	10995	7
All exams	58	6119	6
Exams with detected collaborations	3	612	6

Table 1: Number of exams having the watermarking feature enabled (and having questions that allow watermark embedding) together with their number of participants and detected collaborations.

Within these 58 exams, six participants in three exams were detected by the system having copied and pasted an answer from someone else (Table 1). That means, we know of twelve students in total (0.2% out of 6119 participants) who collaborated without permission (one sharing their answer and the other one copying/pasting the answer in their own text fields). As a consequence, we provided the teachers with the evidence and recommended that these students should not pass their exams. In addition, one pair of students was found having been collaborating during a mock exam, which was not forbidden. We noticed that the detected collaborations took place only in exams that consisted of no or a very small number of random questions/variants (only two or three random questions per topic and difficulty level).

As we are not aware of anyone who posted screenshots of their question/answers on a public website, we did not had a chance to uncover anyone with the help of the website background watermarking. Probably, the psychological level of making the students aware of a fraud detection system also matters a lot, but we are not able to substantiate this effect.

There is a possibility that many students could have cheated through other means (e.g. by sharing screenshots in private chats, removing our text watermark, meeting in the same room despite the COVID-19 lockdowns or hire a ghostwriter) that are hard or impossible to be detected. However, building a large question bank still seems to be an effective and reasonable way to stop students from easily collaborating with themselves during a remote exam. Even when they still try to work together, they need to spend more time on finding and comparing their questions and answers in the chat log.

5 SUMMARY

Our text watermarking system is able to reliably detect a certain way of cheating and it was able to unveil a few forbidden collaborations, although the students were made aware of it shortly before they started their exam. We cannot substantiate this psychological effect and whether students still cheated through other means that this system cannot detect. Since these collaborations occurred only in exams with few to no random questions, we suggest building a large question bank with at least four random questions/variants as a way to prevent students from easily collaborating. As we do not know of a student who published screenshots of their question and answers, our website background watermarking could not reveal fraud. We only embedded the watermarks in short answer, numerical, calculated, and cloze question types, but it could also be applied to more. Notably, essay questions and other multiline answer fields could be covered in future work.

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